

GRAPHENE NANOPARTICLES EMBEDDED IN A POLYMERIC MATRIX FOR ADDED-VALUE MULTIFUNCTIONALITY

Biswajit Basu¹, Fabio Casciati², Sara Casciati³, Biqiong Chen⁴, Andrea Spagnoli⁵ and Yahui Wen⁴

¹Department of Civil, Structural and Environmental Engineering, Trinity College,
College Green, Dublin 2, Ireland

Email: basub@tcd.ie, web page: <http://people.tcd.ie/basub>

²Department of Civil and Architectural Engineering DICAR, University of Pavia,
via Ferrata 3, 27100 Pavia, Italy

Email: fabio@dipmec.unipv.it, web page: <http://dipmec.unipv.it>

³Department of Civil and Architectural Engineering DICAR, University of Catania,
piazza Federico di Svevia, 96100, Siracusa, Italy

Email: sacasci@unict.it, web page: <http://unict.academia.edu/saracasciati>

⁴Department of Materials Science and Engineering,
University of Sheffield, Mappin Street, Sheffield S1 3JD, United Kingdom

Email: biqiong.chen@sheffield.ac.uk, web page: <https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/materials/staff/bchen>

⁵Dipartimento di Ingegneria Civile, dell'Ambiente, del Territorio e Architettura DICATEA
Parco Area delle Scienze, 181/A, 43100, Parma, Italy

Email: andrea.spagnoli@unipv.it, web page: <http://www.unipr.it/~spagnoli/>

Keywords: Composite materials, Conductivity, Identification, Mechanical Properties, Laboratory Testing

ABSTRACT

Material research is developing along different patterns, each of them being characterized by the Technology Readiness Level. The European Union adopted a scale for this purpose and the challenging level here is #5: “technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)”. It is obviously one step further TRL4, which requires the laboratory validation. In this contribution, graphene nanoparticle-embedded polymer composites will be mechanically and electrically tested in a benchmark effort to prove the technology readiness level. The next step will be to add multifunctional features to the successful specimens and to assess their performance mainly in view of extreme environmental conditions.

1 INTRODUCTION

The authors gathered in a research team in order to mature the ability to satisfy some requirements formulated by the European Union (EU) Research Directorate within the ongoing research program, named Horizon 2020, with a focus on the development of multifunctional materials. The first requirement is quite general and covers the degree of readiness on an innovative product: it is specified by the term “Technology Readiness Level” (TRL), for which a specific scale was adopted. The level, which this research team intends to afford, is the fifth one which states: “technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)”. It is obviously one step further TRL4, which requires the laboratory validation.

The second requirement represents a sort of final goal for the team effort: to define scenarios of extreme environmental conditions and to be able to compare the material performances by suitable schemes of laboratory testing.

The research group from Trinity College Dublin has significant research experience in developing self-healing composite structures. The focus has been on the use of cyanoacrylate for wind turbine blades [1][2][3]. At the University of Sheffield, there is a deep insight in developing high-performance polymer nanocomposites including polymer-graphene nanocomposites, for both engineering and biomedical applications [4][5]. The University of Catania and Pavia matured expertise in fatigue testing of smart materials, as shape memory alloys and rubbers among others. Finally, the research group at the University of Parma manages both the experimental aspects and the material numerical modelling.

The paper presented at the ICCM20, which will be made available in open access via the website of ICCM (<http://www.iccm-central.org/>), is regarded as a first step of sharing ideas and attitudes within the international community.

This paper reports some aspects of a work-in-progress for embedding graphene nanoparticles in a polymeric matrix with a view to add multi-functionality.

2 GENERAL SPECIFICATIONS

2.1 Reference material

Unsaturated polyester (UPE), one of the most important thermosetting polymers, is widely used in wind turbine blades, car body panels, adhesives, coatings, etc. due to its reasonably good mechanical performance, excellent chemical and moisture resistance, low cost, and easy processing capability [6]. However, it shows lower stiffness and strength compared to some other important thermosetting polymers such as epoxy. In order to improve its properties, different types of filler like clay, carbon fibres and carbon nanotubes have been used [7][8]. Graphene is a one atom-thick sheet of sp^2 carbon atoms [9]. Because of its high intrinsic electron mobility, Young's modulus, thermal conductivity, and specific surface area, graphene has recently attracted significant attention as a promising nanofiller in composite materials for a wide variety of applications [4][10][11]. In this work, graphene oxide (GO) with abundant oxygenated functional groups on its surface will be used to mix with UPE resin. GO is expected to be reduced into graphene (or reduced graphene oxide) during the heat treatment stage, restoring part of the electrical conductivity of pristine graphene sheets and hence improving both the mechanical and electrical properties of the polymer matrix.

The unsaturated polyester resin used in this work will be CRYSTIC D3601 from Scott Bader Company Limited. Methyl ethyl ketone peroxide and cobalt salt G (1 wt.% cobalt 2-ethylhexanoate in styrene), also provided by Scott Bader, will be used as the initiator and the accelerator respectively. Both neat UPE polymer and UPE-graphene composites will be prepared. Rectangular and cylindrical samples will be produced by casting resin into silicone moulds followed by curing and post-cure heat treatment.

2.2 Extreme scenarios

Without being exhaustive, the extreme scenarios to be considered include the following:

- i) Pressure;
- ii) Temperature;
- iii) Ice.

For the purpose of illustration, one refers to technical problems related with the wind turbines [12][13]. Pressure is the result of wind turbulence whose spectrum affects a well defined range of frequencies: the multifunctionality of the material has to be unaffected by high amplitude oscillations of pressure within the frequency range of interest. Temperature is related to the day-night, winter-summer excursions. The latter one, in Northern Europe, can span over more than 100 °C. Finally ice produces a quite complex effect, modifying on one side the material features and initiating significant

deviation in the structural response as resulting from the modification of the system natural frequencies.

3 SPECIMEN FEATURES

The policy is to always produce specimens of both the basic polymer and the composite obtained by adding nanoparticles to it. This guarantees to detect from the two tests the features of the basic composite and how they are changed by the additive.

Figure 1: Specimens conceived for the tension (with end taps added before testing) (left) and compression (right) tests.

Moreover the shape of the specimens will be selected to be compatible with the production technology. For example, the rectangular bars will have a length of ~80 mm, a width of ~10 mm and a thickness of ~2 mm, while the cylindrical samples will have a diameter of ~10 mm with a height of over 10 mm. Where appropriate, dog-bone shaped samples will be tested in tension in replacement of the rectangular bars. These mechanical properties are pursued by tests in span control, with the grip solutions illustrated in Figure 2. On the right photograph one can also see the thermal chamber to be used when the temperature effects have to be studied.

Figure 2: Flat disks grips used for the compression test on cylindrical specimens (left) and hinged grips to be used in tension tests to avoid undesired specimen compressions.

It is worth noticing that a major issue in these tests arises when also the material conductivity has to be estimated. This requires a full electrical isolation that must be achieved without sliding at the grips and without altering the testing environment.

4 LABORATORY TESTS

Some preparatory tests were planned in advance of the main testing to decide on the details of the testing where fully designed and developed composite materials will be used.

An initial simple compression test does not show usually significant differences between the basis polymer and the composite material. Figure 3 shows the preliminary result of such a test on the latter one. Moving to the tension tests, things can be changed dramatically, with the additive increasing the brittleness of the polymer, which can cause problems in the gripping. Other shapes of samples may be tested in the future.

In compression, cycles of loading-unloading of increasing amplitude (except the last one) are applied to the basis polymer giving rise to the provocative representation of Figure 4. The initial toe region could be from the sliding between the sample and the plate and/or the defects in the sample. The operator carrying out the test should be instructed on how to improve the alignment of the plates and the sample as well as the sample surface. One could also decide to correct this toe zone when defining the loading cycle.

Moreover, the shift of the loading path could suggest to adopt a training policy as it is normally done when testing shape memory alloys which exhibit a similar trend [12][13].

Further sample preparation and mechanical and electrical tests of the samples are planned, and the representative results will be obtained and presented on the forthcoming ICCM20 conference.

Figure 3: Preliminary result from a preparatory compression test on a composite material.

Commentato [o1]: I deleted this because we have already had strain data in the figure.

Figure 4: Preliminary results from a preparatory tension tests on the basic polymer: cycles of loading-unloading of increasing amplitude except the last one.

To afford the extreme condition scenarios introduced in sub-section 2.2, the following tests should be planned, always detecting mechanical and electrical properties. They should be repeated at different temperatures.

- 1) Training effect;
- 2) Aging effect [14];
- 3) Test under cycles of loading-unloading at different frequencies;
- 4) Fatigue of constant amplitude.

A further level of sophistication would cover the investigation of the performance sensitivity to the progress of fracture within the specimen [15].

5 CONCLUSIONS

The paper organizes the working plans which are supposed to lead the authors from the material production to the “certification” of a “Technology Readiness Level” of 5 when the requirement of a satisfactory performance in extreme conditions is demanded.

When designing multifunctional materials, the importance of preserving evidence of the basic polymer is outlined first. Topics such as training and aging are discussed and the associated tests defined. Dependency of the properties on the frequency of loading-unloading cycles and the way fatigue tests have to be conceived are investigated. The role of temperature and icing is also emphasized.

Focus is on the variation of the composite conductivity with all these quantities which determine the different scenarios of use. The testing process follows as a consequence.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Each author acknowledges the availability of research grants from his/her own academic affiliation.

REFERENCES

- [1] O.Fifo, K.Ryan, B.Basu Glass fibre polyester composite with in vivo vascular channel for use in self healing, 2014 *Smart Mater. Struct.* 23 (9), pp 1-8.
- [2] O.Fifo, K.Ryan, B.Basu Investigations on the effectiveness of cyanoacrylate adhesive for repair of fibre-reinforced polymer laminates under different environmental conditions, 2014 *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 48(21) 2657–2668
- [3] O.Fifo, K.Ryan, B.Basu Application of self healing technique to fibre reinforced polymer wind turbine blade, 2015 *Smart Structures and Systems* in press.
- [4] C. Wan, B. Chen: Reinforcement and interface of polymer/graphene oxide nanocomposites. *Journal of Materials Chemistry*, **22**, 2012, pp.3637–3646.
- [5] R. Justin, B. Chen: Strong and conductive chitosan–reduced graphene oxide nanocomposites for transdermal drug delivery. *Journal of Materials Chemistry B*, **2**, 2014, pp. 3759–3770.
- [6] B. Dholakiya, "Unsaturated Polyester Resin for Specialty Applications" in "Polyester", edited by H. E.-D. M. Saleh, InTech, 2012.
- [7] S. H. Aziz, M. P. Ansell, S. J. Clarke, and S. R. Panteny, "Modified polyester resins for natural fibre composites," *Composites and Science Technology*, **65**, 2005, pp. 525–535, 2005.
- [8] L. Tibiletti, C. Longuet, L. Ferry, P. Coutelen, A. Mas, J. J. Robin, and J. M. Lopez-Cuesta, "Thermal degradation and fire behaviour of unsaturated polyesters filled with metallic oxides," *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, **96**, 2011, pp. 67–75.
- [9] A. K. Geim, K. S. Novoselov, "The rise of graphene," *Nature Materials*, **6**, 2007, pp. 183–191, 2007.
- [10] Y. Zhu, S. Murali, W. Cai, X. Li, J. W. Suk, J. R. Potts, and R. S. Ruoff, "Graphene and graphene oxide: synthesis, properties, and applications.," *Advanced Materials*, **22**, 2010, pp. 3906–3924, 2010.
- [11] O. C. Compton and S. T. Nguyen, "Graphene oxide, highly reduced graphene oxide, and graphene: Versatile building blocks for carbon-based materials," *Small*, **6**, 2010, pp. 711–723.
- [12] A. Spagnoli, L. Montanari (2013) Along-wind simplified analysis of wind turbines through a coupled blade-tower model, *Wind and Structures*, **20** (17), 2013, pp. 589-608.
- [13] Z. Zhang, B. Basu, Nielsen S.R.K., Tuned liquid column dampers for mitigation of edgewise vibrations in rotating wind turbine blades, *Structural Control & Health Monitoring*, **22** (2), 2015, pp. 500-517.
- [14] V. Torra, G. Carreras, S. Casciati, P. Terriault, On the NiTi wires in dampers for stayed cables, *Smart Structures and Systems*, **13** (3), 2014, pp. 353-374.
- [15] F. Casciati, S. Casciati, L. Faravelli, Fatigue Damage Accumulation in a Cu-based Shape Memory Alloy: Preliminary Investigation, *CMC – Computers Materials & Continua*, **23** (3), 2011, pp. 287-306.
- [16] F. Casciati, L. Faravelli, Experimental investigation on the aging of the base isolator elastomeric component, *Acta Mechanica*, **223** (8), 2012, pp.1633-1643.
- [17] R. Brighenti, A. Carpinteri, A Spagnoli, D. Scorza, Cracking Behaviour of Fibre-Reinforced Cementitious Composites: a Comparison between Continuous and Discrete Computational Approach, *Engineering fracture Mechanics*, **12** (103), 2013, pp. 103- 114.

Commentato [o2]: The following references are not in the same format.